

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

INTEGRATED METHODS OF CONTROL OF THE *LEPTINOTARSA DECEMLINEATA* SAY, 1824 (COLEOPTERA: CHRYSOMELIDAE) IN MOUNTAINOUS AREAS

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Abstract

The potato culture spreads widely in the private and farmer economies in many countries, including Azerbaijan. But the research of many scientists shows that tons of products are lost under an influence of the harmful organisms. In this connection the integrated chemical and biological control methods of combating of the Colorado potato beetle's (*Leptinotarsa decemlineata* Say, 1824) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) larva were applied in the Gazakh-Tovuz region of Azerbaijan. The researches were carried out in 2014-2018. In order to control *L. decemlineata* larva during the research years Mostar 20 SP (0.02; 0.04; 0.06 kg/ha), Mosetam 20 SP (0.02; 0.04; 0.06 kg/ha), Ramplan 20 SP (0.02; 0.04; 0.06 kg/ha), Cypersan 25 CS (0.2; 0.4; 0.6 l/ha) and other preparations have been tested and the optimal doses have been determined. Karate Zeon 5 CS (0.1 l/ha) preparation was applied under a standard variant. The biological efficiency was 83.3 – 95.8% under a version of pickling with Mosetam 20 SP preparation (0.06 kg/ha). 0.5; 1.0; 1.5% solution of the Bitoxybacillin (BTB) and Boverin microbiological preparations were used against *L. decemlineata* under five variants and four repetitions during early sowing. 1.0 and 1.5% solution of the Boverin microbiological preparation showed 50% biological efficiency. The preparations being applied against Colorado potato beetle have a high biological efficiency in the indicated doses, don't exert any phytotoxic influence on plants.

Keywords: Colorado potato beetle, integrated methods, pest management, plant protection

1. Introduction

The UN General Assembly Conference on Environmental Protection and Development in Rio de Janeiro in June 1992 received a document entitled "Agenda 21" of the Long Agenda for future action on a global scale. The purpose of this document is to prepare for the challenges of the 21st century (Olsen, 2014; Devaux et al., 2014). This program introduces the importance of soil, water and atmospheric degradation, forest protection and conservation of biodiversity. One of the responsibilities of humanity is to provide the world's population with agricultural products. Research shows that there is an average of 48 grams of protein per day per capita, but this figure should be 100 grams. More than 60% of the population suffers from malnutrition, 30% of them starve (Gerasimova, 2007).

The modern development of human society is closely related to environmental problems, these problems also exist in agriculture. To meet the needs of the world's population in agricultural products, various works are carried out. One of these measures is to increase the productivity of agricultural plants. Various structural pesticides and agrochemical substances are widely used to increase yields, which causes environmental pollution. (Ester et al., 2011; Ulyanenko et al., 2015; Popov et al., 2015; Ropek and Kolodziejczyk, 2018; Gallego et al., 2020; Dupuis et al., 2021; Taylor and Dawson, 2021). More than 300 million tons of fertilizers and 4 million tons of pesticides are annually introduced into the agro- and biocenosis, which causes imbalance in the biosphere (Ecological engineering for pest management, 2004; Hasanpanah, 2012). Since the middle of the last century, measures have been taken against the pesticide syndrome, which later became known as integrated control measures. Scientific and

technical development requires the improvement of integrated control. The use of this system should guarantee the preservation of the ecological balance in the environment, the non-accumulation of toxic residues in agricultural products, the creation of normal living conditions for living organisms in biocenoses, and so on.

Recently, the integrated control system has sometimes been referred to as "population management". This shows that the purpose of this system is not to eliminate pests, but to protect the biosphere as a whole. Therefore, the application of the system of integrated control measures should be carried out in the form of a scheme of sequential (corresponding to local conditions) consistency of predictive, quarantine, agrotechnical, genetic, biological, mechanical, physical and chemical control methods.

Our investigations show that the following problems exist in potato growing in the Gazakh-Tovuz region of Azerbaijan: 1) incorrect definition of the sowing time of the vegetative material; 2) detection by farmers of potato bulb degeneration, abnormal development and other indications; 3) thickening of the tillage layer during various agrotechnical measures; 4) chaotic development of the harmful organisms in agroecosis; 5) non-germination of 60–70% buds on the vegetative tillage material (Huseynov, 2012). Based on the results of our research, it can be said that in order to obtain a high and sustainable potato yield in the studied territories, it is necessary to determine the species composition, distribution area, bioecological characteristics of the Colorado potato beetle (*Leptinotarsa decemlineata* Say, 1824) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) and the damage caused by them. In addition to agronomic measures, the

preparation of effective control measures is of great importance for the development of potato growing in this region.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Object

The area of the Gazakh-Tovuz economic region is 15% of the zone of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The region is located at a latitude of 40° 80' and 41° 43' North, at a longitude of 44° 95' and 46° 82' East. The plain, foothill and mountainous zones of Gazakh, Shamkir, Tovuz, Aghstafa, Gadabay districts include in Gazakh-Tovuz region. A total area of the region is 546.7 thousand hectares. The rational temperatures totally reach 3800–4400°C. The length of vegetation period is 213–210 days. An annual quantity of the precipitations changes by 250–810 mm. In terms of humidity, the region belongs to the semi-humid and arid zone. Our research was carried out in the mountainous zone of Gazakh-Tovuz region, at an altitude of 500-1000 m above sea level. The mountain-brown, mountain-gray-brown soils widely spread in the research object.

2.2. Methods

To determine the percentage of damage to the surface organs of plants, 20 samples were examined in the diagonal direction of the field and 5 plants in each sample. In this case, the distance between the samples was taken to be the same. The percentage of plant damage was calculated using the following formula (1) (Shafibayov, 1964):

$$P = \frac{n \cdot 100}{N}, \quad (1)$$

Where “P” is percentage of damage to tubers, shoots and leaves, “n” is a number of damaged tubers, shoots and leaves, “N” is a total number of the examined tubers, shoots and leaves, “100” is a conversion coefficient to percentage.

The economic injury level of the pests over the generations was calculated according to the formula (2) by Tansky (1988):

$$EIL = \frac{E \cdot A \cdot P \cdot ST \cdot PT \cdot SEC}{FP \cdot SP \cdot PL \cdot BE \cdot SI} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{HE}{SP}\right), \quad (2)$$

Where “EIL” is a economic injury level (number), “E” is a expenses for control (AZN (Azerbaijani manat)), “A” is a additional expenses (AZN), “P” is a profitable (%), “ST” is a species tolerance, “PT” is a physiological tolerance, “SEC” is a social-ecological coefficient, “FP” is the factual product (kg), “SP” is a selling price of product (AZN), “PL” is a product loss per person (kg), “BE” is a biological efficiency (%), “SI

“ is a surviving individuals, “HE” is a harvest expenses (AZN).

During the years of research, it was planned to carry out chemical control of the main pests affecting the surface organs and tubers of the potato plant. The experiments were carried out in four replicates according to 5 variants. The area of each repetition was taken equal to 50 m². Observations of the biological effectiveness of the preparations and calculations were performed after 5; 10; 15; 20 days of the disinfection and before harvest. The biological efficiency of the preparations was determined by the Abbott formula (3) (1925).

$$BE = \frac{(N-n) \cdot 100}{N}, \quad (3)$$

Where “BE” is a biological efficiency of the preparation (%), “N” is the number of the pests after disinfection in the control variant, “n” is the number of the pests after disinfection in the experimental version, “100” is a conversion coefficient to percentage.

3. Results and discussion

It should be noted that the Colorado potato beetle more damages the potato plant in the early stages of plant development. This is due to the high nutritional value of potatoes at the first stage of development and the low green mass of the plant. Therefore, it is very important to carry out the activities included in the system of integrated control measures at the optimal time. Otherwise, plants damaged by pests at the beginning of the growing season will have difficulties with the formation of a crop in the next period of development.

In order to establish the economic injury level of *L. decemlineata* during the years of research, experiments were carried out consisting of four variants in potato sowings from the Sabirkend of the Shamkir region and Slavyanka of the Gadabay region. By studying the bioecological characteristics of *L. decemlineata* in the research area at an altitude of 900-1000 m above sea level, a bioclimogram was compiled. (Fig. 1). As can be seen from the bioclimogram, an increase in precipitation by 20-60 mm contributes to the development of pests. Unfortunately, the amount of precipitation in this region is often higher than these parameters, which creates a better environment for the development of *L. decemlineata*. The development of one generation of the Colorado potato beetle lasts 48-55 days.

Note: 1. I-XII-show months.

2. The blue line shows the trajectory of the pests development.

Fig. 1. Boiclimogram of *L. decemlineata* in the potato sowings of the zones till 900- 1000 m above sea-level (Shamkir district, Sabirkend settlement).

The experiments consisting of four versions were also carried out in the Slavyanka village. While studying the economic injury level, a quantity of the pests (larvae) and the degree of plant damage has been compared with the expenses for the chemical control. For this purpose, splashing with the Koru-Alpha (0.03 1/400 liters of water) preparation was performed under the second, third and fourth (control) variants during

the first generation development, under the first, third and fourth (control) versions at a period of the second generation development, under the first, second and fourth (control) variants during the third generation development (Fasulati, 1971). For each of the experimental and control variants, the productivity of damaged and healthy plants were determined (Table 1).

Table 1

Disinfection scheme.

area generation	I	II	III	IV
I	-*	+*	+	+
II	+	-	+	+
III	+	+	-	+

*“-“ – disinfection was not performed, “+“ – disinfection was performed.

According to the sowing scheme (70 cm x 30 cm measure), the product loss and its cost were revealed (Table 1). Besides, the expenses for the chemical control were exacted. The expenses for the chemical control in this generation amounted to \$27 (Klisenko et al., 2008).

After the product loss was exacted the economic injury level of the pests over the generations was calculated by formula 4 (Tansky, 1988):

$$EIL = \frac{47 \cdot 1.1 \cdot 3 \cdot 1 \cdot 0.8 \cdot 1}{300 \cdot 50 \cdot 0.0042 \cdot 0.85 \cdot 0.15} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{2}{50}\right) = \frac{124}{8.03} \cdot 1.04 = 15.4 \cdot 1.04 = 16.0 \text{ number } \frac{\text{larva}}{10} \text{ plant (I generation), (4)}$$

$$EIL = \frac{47 \cdot 1.1 \cdot 3 \cdot 1 \cdot 0.8 \cdot 1}{300 \cdot 50 \cdot 0.0035 \cdot 0.91 \cdot 0.09} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{2}{50}\right) = \frac{124}{4.3} \cdot 1.04 = 28.8 \cdot 1.04 = 29.9 \text{ number } \frac{\text{larva}}{10} \text{ plant (II and III generations)}$$

Calculations showed that when 15-16 larvae were found on 100 plants and the amount of damage was up to 25% in the first generation, the cost of the lost product (\$66) was 2.3 times higher than the cost of chemical

control (\$28). In the second and third generations, the cost of the lost product was \$60 (2nd generation) and \$57 (3rd generation), respectively. Damage of 25% (in generation I) and 50% (in generations II and III) of the

potato plant by the *L. decemlineata* was identified as an economic injury level of the pests over the generations (Table 2).

Table 2.

Variants (generation)	The number of larvae per 100 plants or the percentage of plant damage, %	productivity, kg / ha	product loss in comparison with the control, kg	product loss per one larva, kg	Product loss from hectare		Number of larva in hectare
					kg	AZN	
I generation	5% or 7–8 larva	37900	0.180	0.024	100	50	4145.8
	5–25% or 15–16 larva	37780	0.397	0.025	220	110	8568.0
	25–50% or 29–30 larva	34490	6.349	0.215	3510	175.5	16307.0
	50–75% or 60–60 larva	32670	9.642	0.154	5330	266.5	34548.7
	more than 75% or 120–125 larva	30600	13.386	0.109	7400	370	67715.5
II generation	5% or 7–8 larva	37960	0.072	0.009	40	20	4145.8
	5–25% or 15–16 larva	37930	0.126	0.008	70	35	8568.0
	25–50% or 29–30 larva	37800	0.361	0.012	200	100	16307.0
	50–75% or 60–65 larva	34200	6.874	0.109	3800	190	34548.7
	more than 75% or 120–125 larva	32200	10.492	0.085	5800	254	67715.5
III generation	5% or 7-8 larva	37980	0.036	0.004	20	10	4145.8
	5–25 % or 15–16 larva	37960	0.072	0.009	40	20	8568.0
	25–50% or 29–30 larva	37810	1.628	0.055	190	95	16307.0
	50–75% or 60–60 larva	34800	5.788	0.092	3200	160	34548.7
	more than 75% or 120–125 larva	33720	7.742	0.063	4280	214	67715.5
Control	-	38000	-	-	-	-	-

As can be seen from Fig. 2, *L. decemlineata* injures the potato plant in the early stages of plant development.

Fig. 2. Economically harmful limit progeny of *L. decemlineata*.

3.1. Chemical control measures against *L. decemlineata*: application of the selective pesticides

When developing measures to combat *L. decemlineata*, we got acquainted with the research of internal and foreign scientists of recent years and took into account the results of their research (Goehring and Oberhauser 2002; McSorley 2003; Munyiri and Ishikawa, 2004; Shelton, 2004; Bosa et al., 2005; Saxena et al.,

2006; Kakharov, 2008; Agansonova et al., 2011; Mal-yuga et al., 2013; Fisechko, 2013; Butov and Boeva, 2013; Abrosimova et al., 2014; Suffert and Ward 2014; Wierzbowska et al., 2016; Zarzecka and Gugala, 2018). For the purpose to control *L. decemlineata* larva during the research years Mostar 20 SP (0.02; 0.04; 0.6 kg/ha), Mosectam (0.02; 0.04 ; 0.06 kg/ha), Ramplan 20 SP (0.02; 0.04 ; 0.06 kg/ha), Cypersan 25 CS (0.3; 0.5; 9.7

I/ha), Confidor 20 LS (0.3; 0.5; 0.7 I/ha), Supercor 2.5 CS (0.1; 0.2; 0.3 I/ha), Koru-Alpha (0.01; 0.03; 0.05 I/ha), Fastkill (0.2; 0.3; 0.41 I/ha), Cyperkiller (0.2; 0.3; 0.4 I/ha), Constar (0.2; 0.3; 0.4 I/ha) preparations were tested, and their optimal doses were established. The test-experimental works were performed under 5 variants and 4 repetitions over the years, Under a standard variant Karate Zeon 5 CS (0.1 I/ha) preparation was applied (Table 3). Each secondary area was 250 m². To determine the biological effectiveness of insecticides after 5–10–15–20 days of disinfection, observations and calculations were carried out in the experimental and control variants.

The highest biological efficiency has been noted in the fifth day after disinfection. While a quantity of the larva under the variant of the disinfection with Mostar 20 SP insecticide (0.06 kg/ha) was 0–2 numbers for the 5th day, this index under the control variant was 18–27 numbers, the biological efficiency of preparation was 88.8–100%. A quantity of the larva under the variant of disinfection with Mosectam preparation (0.06 kg/ha) was noted 1–3 numbers, but under the control

variant 18–27 numbers and the biological efficiency of the preparation was 83.3–95.8 %. The biological efficiency was 94.4–100 % in splashing with the Ramplan preparation (0.06 kg/ha), Cypersan insecticide (0.4 I/ha) showed 83.3–91.6 % biological efficiency (Fig. 3). The biological efficiency of Decis insecticide (0.4 I/ha) was 83.3–91.6 %, Bulldog preparation (0.5 I/ha) correspondingly was 88.8–100 %, Calypso (1.81/ha) – 94.4–100 %, Cartoon M preparation (1.5 I/ha) - 83.3–95.8 % and so on. The biological efficiency of standard variant (Karate Zeon (0.1 I/ha)) was 83.3–91.6%.

As it is seen from Table 3 that an impact period of the preparations gradually decreases over the days. Therefore, the economical injury limit must be noticed while fixing a fight time. Otherwise, the control must be necessary against one generation several times. Researches have shown that to prevent the development of pesticide resistance in the Colorado potato beetle, it is desirable to use alternating preparations of pyrethroid origin and other methods of control (Mammadova and Huseynov, 2012).

Fig. 3. Biological efficiency of preparations against *L. decemlineata*.

3.2. Biological control measures against *L. decemlineata*

The integrated use of biological control agents in integrated pest control measures for agricultural plants increases the economic rationality and agricultural value of these agents. On the other hand, biological agents prevent the pollution of the environment and the product with pesticides and ensure the maintenance of the ecological balance in the environment.

During the research years the protective strips and microbiological preparations (Bitoxybacillin (BTB), Boverin) have been tested. For the application of protective strips, attractive plants were chosen first. Research has shown that *L. decemlineata* feeds more on eggplants and potatoes than on cultivated and wild plants belonging to the *Solanaceae* family, they aren't interested in other plants. Therefore the eggplant was

used as a protective strip for potato agrocenosis. One of the reasons the eggplant is used as a protective strip is because it has a long growing season. So, the stripe being sown in the early spring can be used both in early and in the summer tillage, as well as in the spring tillage. For this, experiments were carried out in two versions and four repetitions on planting potatoes in private farms of Sabirkend village of the Shamkir district. In the first variant, early planting of eggplants (second decade of March, planting seedlings under a shelter) was carried out along the edges of the field. The second option was the control one. In the first case, measures to combat the Colorado potato beetle were carried out using eggplants. In the second variant, control measures were carried out directly on potato crops (Table 4).

Table 3

Chemical control of the *L. decemlineata* over the generations (2014 – 2022)

Variants	Name of the preparation	Expense norm of the preparation	The number of the pests after disinfection (in 100 plants)					Biological efficiency of the preparation, %					The number of the pests after disinfection (in 100 plants)					Biological efficiency of the preparation, %								
			Over days					Over days					Over days					Over days								
			5	10	15	20		5	10	15	20		5	10	15	20		5	10	15	20					
I	Mostar 20 SP	0.06 kg/ha	2	3	4	7	88.8	85.7	84.6	77.4	100	92.8	84.8	83.7	0	3	6	7	100	91.4	85.3	84.0				
II	Mosetam	0.06 kg/ha	3	5	7	9	83.3	76.1	73.0	70.9	1	4	8	11	95.8	85.7	75.7	70.2	2	4	7	9	92.5	88.5	82.9	79.5
III	Ramplan 20 SP	0.06 kg/ha	1	3	4	6	94.4	85.7	84.6	80.6	0	2	5	7	100	92.8	84.8	81.0	0	3	6	8	100	91.4	85.3	81.8
IV	Cypersan 25 CS	0.4 l/ha	3	4	6	11	83.3	80.9	76.9	64.5	2	5	8	9	91.6	92.1	75.7	75.6	3	5	8	10	88.8	85.7	80.4	77.2
V	Decis	0.4 l/ha	3	6	8	11	83.3	71.4	69.2	64.5	2	3	6	9	91.6	89.2	81.8	75.6	3	5	6	8	88.8	85.7	85.3	81.8
VI	Bulldog ES 2.5 CS	0.5 l/ha	2	3	5	6	88.8	85.7	80.7	80.6	0	2	4	7	100	92.8	87.8	81.0	0	3	5	9	100	91.4	87.8	79.5
VII	Calypso 48 CS	1.8 l/ha	1	2	4	6	94.4	90.4	84.6	80.6	0	2	3	6	100	92.8	90.9	83.7	0	3	6	8	100	91.4	85.3	81.8
VIII	Cartoon M	1.5 l/ha	3	5	7	9	83.3	76.1	73.0	70.9	1	4	8	11	95.8	85.7	75.7	70.2	2	4	7	9	92.5	88.5	82.9	79.5
IX	Confidor 20 CS	0.7 l/ha	0	2	3	5	100	90.4	88.4	83.8	0	0	4	7	100	100	87.8	81.0	0	2	3	7	100	94.2	92.6	84.0
X	Supercor 2.5 CS	0.2 l/ha	2	3	5	7	88.8	85.7	80.7	77.4	0	2	5	8	100	92.8	84.8	78.3	1	4	7	9	96.2	88.5	82.9	79.5
XI	Koru-Alpha	0.03 l/ha	2	4	7	10	88.8	80.9	73.0	67.7	2	5	7	10	91.6	92.1	78.7	72.9	3	6	8	9	88.8	82.5	80.4	79.5
XII	Fastkill	0.4 l/ha	2	3	5	6	88.8	85.7	80.7	80.6	0	2	4	7	100	92.8	87.8	81.0	0	3	5	9	100	91.4	87.8	79.5
XIII	Folidol	1.0 l/ha	0	2	3	5	100	90.4	88.4	83.8	0	0	4	7	100	100	87.8	81.0	0	2	3	7	100	94.2	92.6	84.0
XIV	Cyperkiller	0.4 l/ha	3	5	7	9	83.3	76.1	73.0	70.9	1	4	8	11	95.8	85.7	75.7	70.2	2	4	7	9	92.5	88.5	82.9	79.5
XV	Constar	0.4 l/ha	3	4	6	11	83.3	80.9	76.9	64.5	2	5	8	9	91.6	92.1	75.7	75.6	3	5	8	10	88.8	85.7	80.4	77.2
XVI	Karate Zeon CS (standard)	0.1 l/ha	3	6	8	11	83.3	71.4	69.2	64.5	2	3	6	9	91.6	89.2	81.8	75.6	3	5	6	8	88.8	85.7	85.3	81.8
XVII	Control	–	18	21	26	31	–	–	–	–	24	28	33	37	–	–	–	–	27	35	41	44	–	–	–	–

The carried out investigations showed that the use of protective strips, along with maintaining an ecological balance and growing organic products, also increases productivity. This was due to the fact that in the sprayed variant (control) the plants were stressed by the

sprayed working solution and growth was inhibited. One of the advantages of using protective strips is that it reduces the pesticide load of the pests in invasion years and does not accumulate toxic residues in the product.

Table 4Application of the protective strip against *L. decemlineata* in the early plantings.

Variants	Name of the preparation	Expense norms, kg/ha	Number of the pests after disinfection, number				Biological efficiency of the preparation, %				Productivity, t/ha	Quantity of the toxic residue	
			5	10	15	20	5	10	15	20		10	20
Experiment	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	38.0	-	-
Control	Ramplan	0.06	1	3	4	6	94.4	85.7	84.6	80.6	36.8	0.31	-

The microbiological preparations were tested against *L. decemlineata* during the research years. The microbiological preparations have some superiorities in comparison with the pesticides.

Studies have shown that biopreparations are selective, do not influence on entomophages and pollinating insects, and are not resistant to pests. These preparations are not dangerous for warm-blooded animals and humans and do not have a phytocidal (phytotoxic) effect on agricultural crops (Agansonova et al, 2011; Butov and Boeva, 2013). Microbiological preparations can be used at any stage of plant development, and the waiting period is short.

Bitoxybacillin (*Bacillus thuringiensis*, var. *thuringiensis*), exotoxin (crystal spore mass, dust like, BA-1500 EA/mg. Russian Federation) and Boverin (*Beauveria bassiana*, strain TC 92, fungal blastospores, titer 2 billion spores / gram, Russian Federation) microbiological preparations were tested against *L. decemlineata* in the early plantings in 2014–2018. For this purpose, 0.5; 1.0; 1.5 % solutions of BTB and Boverin were prepared and experiments were performed in five variants and four repetitions. Under the standard variant the Karate Zeon preparation (0.1 l/ha) was used (Table 5).

Table 5Biological efficiency of the microbiological preparations against *L. decemlineata* larva in the early sowings.

Name of the preparation	Variants	Filthiness of the preparation, %	Number of the pests after disinfection, number			Biological efficiency of the preparation, %		
			5	10	15	5	10	15
BTB	I	0.5	8	9	10	-	10	16
BTB	II	1.0	5	4	8	37.5	60	33
BTB	III	1.5	5	4	6	37.5	60	50
Boverin	IV	0.5	8	10	11	-	-	8
Boverin	V	1.0	7	5	8	12	50	33
Boverin	VI	1.5	6	5	7	25	50	41.6
Karate Zeon	VII	0.1 l / ha	1	2	4	87.5	80	66.6
Control	VIII	-	8	10	12	-	-	-

As can be seen from the table 5, 1.0 and 1.5% BTB solution showed 60% biological effectiveness ten days after spraying. But in potato plantings sprayed with 1.0 and 1.5% solution of the microbiological preparation Boverin 10 days after spraying found 50% biological effectiveness. In the control variant (Karate Zeon), the biological efficiency on the fifth day was 87.5%. No phytocidal properties were found in the doses used.

4. Conclusion

Studies have shown that in mountainous areas it is advisable to grow early-maturing potato varieties in fall and spring crops, as well as mid-early and mid-late potato varieties in spring sowing. Agroecosystems growing late-ripening potato varieties in mountainous areas were more susceptible to the negative impact of environmental factors, which increased yield losses and the cost of the product. To control *L. decemlineata* larva, we used integrated control methods, which include chemical and biological measures. From chemical methods, optimal doses of preparations were tested and determined, such as Mostar 20 SP (0.02; 0.04; 0.06

kg/ha), Mosetam 20 SP (0.02; 0.04; 0.06 kg/ha), Ramplan 20 SP (0.02; 0.04; 0.06 kg/ha), Cypersan 25 CS (0.2; 0.4; 0.6 l/ha) and others. From biological preparations were used 0.5; 1.0; 1.5% solution of Bitoxybacillin and Boverin, which showed biological effectiveness of 60 and 50%, respectively. Minimizing the amount of disinfection in an integrated pest control of potato plants had a positive impact on environmental protection. The preparations used against the Colorado potato beetle, in the indicated doses, had high biological effectiveness, did not have any phytotoxic effect on plants, and no toxic residues were found during harvesting.

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